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Numerical study of a copper oxide-based thermochemical heat storage system

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ABSTRACT

A multi-physics model is developed to investigate the performance of high-temperature thermochemical heat storage using the redox looping cycle of CuO/Cu₂O. The model involved flow in free and porous domains, heat transfer in the CuO pellet-packed porous domain (i.e., convection between fluid and pellets, conduction and radiation among pellets), and the endothermic/exothermic reaction. The reaction rate was estimated using a non-parametric kinetic approach which depends on temperature and extent of the reaction. The model was validated within <10 % error margin by the experimental measurements of the temperature inside the reactor and the molar fraction of O₂ at the reactor outlet. The validated model is used to determine the temperature variation and reaction evolution in the pellet-packed domain. In the end, parameter studies were implemented, including inlet mass flow rate, reduction temperature, and oxidation temperature. It was found that a large inlet mass flow brings about a high output temperature, and the reaction runs faster with the larger inlet mass flow. Similarly, increasing the furnace temperature during the reduction process (reduction temperature) also increases the output temperature and accelerates the reaction. In contrast, increasing the furnace temperature during the oxidation process (oxidation temperature) only slightly affected the reaction in the present case. This model could provide useful insights into reactor design, scale-up, and operating conditions to improve the energy storage system performance.

Nomenclature

A_s	specific surface area of the reactive bed, (m ⁻¹)
C_p	specific heat, (J/kg·K)
$c_{\text{surf,CuO}}$	surface site density of CuO, (mol/m ²)
c_i	molar concentration of species i , (mol/m ³)
$c_{\text{pe}, i}$	volumetric site density of species, i (mol/m ³)
D	diameter, (m)
G	irradiation, (W/m ²)
H^0	standard enthalpy change of the reaction at 298.15 K
h_{fc}	heat transfer coefficient between the reactor wall and gas, (W/m ² ·K)
h_{nc}	heat transfer coefficient on the external insulation wall, (W/m ² ·K)
J	outgoing radiation, (W/m ²)
n	refractive index

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(continued)

q	heat flux (W/m^2)
R_i	volumetric reaction rate of species i , ($mol/m^3 \cdot s$)
$R_{pe,i}$	surface reaction rate of species i , ($mol/m^2 \cdot s$)
r	dimensionless radius in Eq. (15), and dimensionless fact in Eq. (20)
S_m	mass source term due to the reaction, ($kg/m^3 \cdot s$)
S_h	heat source term due to the reaction, (W/m^3)
T	temperature, (K)
V	volumetric flow rate, (L/min)
Greek symbols	
α	extent of reaction
α_{fl}	interstitial heat transfer coefficient, ($W/m^2 \cdot K$)
β	Rosseland mean extinction coefficient
ε	porosity
κ	permeability
λ	thermal conductivity, ($W/m \cdot K$)
μ	dynamic viscosity, (Pa-s)
ρ	density, (kg/m^3)
σ	Stepfan-Boltzmann constant ($W/m^2 \cdot K^4$)
ψ	reaction conversion
Subscript	
f	fluid
s	solid
ins	insulation
ms	modified solid
pe	pellet
i	species
rm	reactive material
rb	reactive bed
ib	inert bed
qw	quartz wool

1. Introduction

Thermal energy storage (TES) is a key and promising technology to secure the reliable utilization of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind for heat and power applications. The electricity or heat from renewable resources can be stored in the form of heat and be flexibly released according to the demand, effectively overcoming its inherent challenge of intermittency and demand-supply mismatch. Accordingly, national and international initiatives have been initiated to support TES to accelerate renewable energy deployment for decarbonization and carbon footprint reduction, including REPowerEU in the European Union [1], the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) in the United States [2], and the 14th Five-Year Plan for Renewable Energy in China [3]. Depending on the storage principle, TES can be categorized as sensible heat storage (SHS), latent heat storage (LHS), and thermochemical energy storage (TCES). SHS has been developed on a commercial scale, e.g., molten salts for concentrated solar power (CSP) plants, which stores heat by increasing temperature and has a simple design. However, SHS usually has a low energy storage capacity ($\sim 180 \text{ MJ/m}^3$) [4] and suffers from salt corrosiveness, high material cost, and large storage volumes. In comparison, by employing phase change materials (PCM), LHS achieves a doubled energy storage capacity of $\sim 360 \text{ MJ/m}^3$ and works at near-constant temperatures [5], but it has risks of leakage, phase segregation, container corrosion, etc. On the contrary, TCES based on endothermic/exothermic reactions, is promising because of several benefits, such as high energy storage capacity ($\sim 1800 \text{ MJ/m}^3$ [6]), high thermal stability, and working temperatures ($> 900 \text{ K}$), and low losses. Thus, TCES is currently being broadly explored and it includes gas-gas reactions (e.g., ammonia synthesis), gas-liquid reactions (e.g., ammonium hydrogen sulfate), and gas-solid reactions (e.g., redox system) [7]. Among these, the gas-solid TCES is preferable to modulate renewable energy input/output, and typical reactive materials contain hydroxides, metal hydrides, carbonates, perovskites, and metal oxides [8]. For example, Han et al. [9] investigated the decomposition performance and reaction kinetics of magnesium hydroxide for thermochemical heat storage and constructed a pilot-scale reactor to explore the heat storage performance [10]. It is feasible to scale such TCES up for large-scale utilization due to their abundant availability, thermal/chemical stability, and potential low cost per unit of stored heat. Hydroxides and metal hydrides work at relatively low temperatures, and hydroxides require extra water storage and steam generation sections while hydrides and carbonates need additional hydrogen storage and CO_2 storage, respectively. Such characteristics make these systems more complex and limit their applications to some extent. In contrast, perovskites and metal oxides-based systems perform charging/discharging by redox reactions in which oxygen is available from ambient air, and no separate oxygen storage is needed. Furthermore, they operate at comparatively higher temperatures $> 1000 \text{ K}$ [6], making it a promising technology to secure renewable energy deployment, e.g., concentrated solar power (CSP) applications. Perovskites are nonstoichiometric redox materials which have continuous/quasi-linear partial reduction over a wide temperature range. Babiniec et al. [11] examined the potential of La-Sr-Co-Mn and La-Sr-Co-Fe-based perovskites as thermochemical heat storage materials and obtained a maximum reaction enthalpy of 250 kJ/kg . Chen et al. [12] investigated Sr-based perovskites for heat storage at medium-to-high temperatures, and SrFeO_3 exhibited excellent redox capacity. In addition, CaMnO_3 is identified as one of the most promising perovskites of twelve Ca-Mn and Sr-Fe-based compositions in terms of heat storage

performance [13]. A high reaction enthalpy of 390 kJ/kg was achieved by Al/Ti-doped CaMnO_3 [14], while Mastronardo et al. [15] demonstrated favourable thermodynamic properties of Fe-doped CaMnO_3 . Pein et al. [16], for the first time, tested the thermochemical heat storage performance of foams made of CaMnO_3 , a large step to a large-scale demonstration of monolithic perovskite structures.

In contrast to the perovskites, the metal oxides-based redox takes place at specific equilibrium temperatures. Wong [17] investigated 74 pure metal oxides by thermodynamic calculations and yielded 16 pure metal oxides for TCES. Cr_5O_{12} , Li_2O_2 , and Mg_2O were further excluded because of their low equilibrium reaction temperatures. Fig. 1 comprehensively compares the material cost, energy density, and reaction temperature among the screened 13 metal oxides. It shows that PtO_2 , Rh_2O_3 , and UO_3 are too expensive, which cost two orders of magnitude above the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) target of \$15/kWh. In contrast, BaO , Co_3O_4 , CuO , Mn_2O_3 , Mn_3O_4 , Fe_2O_3 , and V_2O_5 have acceptable costs and preferable energy density, which are suitable for TCES of high temperatures (>1000 K). Agrafiotis et al. [18] carried out lab-scale studies of Co_3O_4 -coated and Mn_2O_3 -coated foams and honeycombs. They proposed cascaded various metal oxides to overcome thermozone temperature distribution within storage blocks. Tescari et al. [19] conducted the first pilot study of Co_3O_4 -based TCES, with the storage unit made of cordierite honeycomb coated with 88 kg of cobalt oxide. The performed 22 charging/discharging cycles achieved a high storage efficiency of 86 %. Carrilo et al. [20] revisited the BaO_2/BaO cycle for TCES by TGA measurements within a temperature range of 773–1173 K, which showed excellent reversibility over 30 cycles and a high energy density of 390 kJ/kg. Karagiannakis et al. [21] experimentally compared the redox performance of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CoO}$ and $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$. It was concluded that cobalt oxide was superior to manganese oxide concerning energy density and redox kinetics. Furthermore, the small particles of $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$ were prone to sintering and degrading their oxidation kinetics because oxygen diffusion was hindered [22] while doping with other metal oxides could modulate surface morphology and boost oxidation kinetics [23]. Hayes et al. [24] presented an experimental demonstration of MgO/MnO mixture-based TCES on a moving-bed reactor which achieved high-temperature (>1273 K) heat storage. Rahmatian et al. [25], for the first time, investigated the TCES performance of MgO/MnO mixtures in a pressure vessel that closely approximates a realistic engineering implementation of a redox storage module, obtaining an average energy storage density of $2428 \pm 469 \text{ MJ/m}^3$ in working temperatures of 1273–1773 K and working pressure of 0.18–11 bar. $\text{CuO}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}$ works at temperatures of around 1300 K which is preferred by emerging CSP plants with high solar power, and it has higher energy storage density and is cheaper than many other metal oxides like BaO_2/BaO , $\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_4$, and $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CoO}$ [17]. Alonso et al. [26] implemented the first experimental campaign of the solar redox reaction of copper oxides in which they developed a rotary kiln storage reactor heated by a solar furnace. It was found that in comparison with the reduction in Argon atmosphere, the redox cycle in air resulted in strong particle coalescence which inhibited the redox reaction. Deutsch et al. [27] investigated the redox kinetics of $\text{CuO}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}$ by TGA and fixed-bed reactor and developed kinetics models using the non-parametric kinetic (NPK) approach. As mentioned before, the sintering of metal oxides degrades the redox performance, and it can be eliminated to some extent by performing the reduction in a non-oxygen atmosphere inside a rotary kiln reactor. Sintering could be a critical issue for the $\text{CuO}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}$ because its reduction temperature (~1300 K) is very close to the Cu_2O melting point (~1500 K). Doping CuO with some sintering-resistant materials is a good way to address this problem. Gigantino et al. [28] prepared yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ)-doped CuO granules. The granules exhibited high redox reversibility over 100 cycles and achieved an energy storage density of 470–615 kJ/kg.

As indicated by the literature aforementioned, tremendous progress has been made regarding metal oxides for high-temperature TCES, explored mostly by TGA analysis and lab-scale reactors. This is an important step towards the practical application of this technology, but many essential insights into reactors are still missing, and not easy to obtain experimentally, e.g., local temperature, species transport, and reaction advancement in reactors, as well as effects of working conditions on the reactor performance. Therefore, numerical models are considerably required to explore these insights, disclosing flow dynamics, heat/mass transfer, and reaction evolution inside reactors, and then shedding light on the reactor design and optimization. Tescari et al. [29] numerically studied the thermal behaviour of a rotary kiln reactor using Co_3O_4 as the reactive material, with particular attention to radiation modelling. In addition to the rotary kiln reactor, fixed-bed reactors are extensively investigated numerically. To improve gas/solid heat transfer, cordierite honeycombs and foams were used as the reaction bed which was coated with reactive materials [18]. Numerical simulations have been carried out to reveal the thermochemical behaviour of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CoO}$ in honeycomb-bed reactors [30–32], and

Fig. 1. Energy density against material cost (data from Ref. [17]).

parametric studies, e.g., porosity, were conducted using the validated model. These studies provided detailed information on the temperature and reaction evolution at the reduction/oxidation stage. In addition, a pellet bed is another type of reactor, in which reactive materials are processed as pellets, including fluidized pellet bed and pellet-packed bed [33]. Wang et al. [34] established a heat and mass transfer model to investigate the thermal reduction of iron–manganese oxide particles in a high-temperature packed-bed solar thermochemical reactor, giving a comprehensive description of the transport phenomena in the reactor. Huang et al. [35] developed a high-fidelity 1D model for a moving magnesium-manganese-oxide bed which presented good predictions of local temperatures and oxygen concentrations at the outlet. Korba et al. [36] experimentally and numerically investigated a moving-bed magnesium-manganese-oxide reactor for thermochemical energy storage aiming to achieve high-temperature heat extraction of more than 1273 K. The performance of the reactor was further investigated through two parametric studies (particle flow rates and gas extraction ratios), which demonstrated a strong dependence of reactor efficiency on both operating parameters. Wang et al. [37] proposed a CFD model to reveal the heat transfer mechanism and heat storage performance of calcium hydroxide/oxide in a shell-tube thermochemical energy storage device. Zheng et al. [38] proposed a computational fluid dynamics-discrete element method (CFD-DEM) model to study the TCES performance of fluidized CaCO_3 pellets under direct concentrated solar irradiation. The model not only reveals the thermal behaviour of the reaction bed reliably but also illustrates the moving of pellets. Hamidi et al. [39] experimentally and numerically explored the reduction of iron-manganese oxide particles in a packed-bed reactor, in which a 2D transient model was developed, accounting for heat transfer, mass transfer, and thermochemical reaction kinetics. The model was capable of predicting oxygen concentration and reaction conversion.

A reliable numerical model is a must for accurate prediction of storage reactor outputs. As mentioned earlier, CuO is a highly suitable material for CSP applications because of its high volumetric energy density ($\sim 2558.7 \text{ MJ/m}^3$), low cost ($\sim \$30.5/\text{MJ}$), and high reaction temperature ($\sim 1393.15 \text{ K}$). The TCES performance of CuO has been experimentally investigated in the literature, but it still lacks numerical modelling to have more insights into the thermal redox behaviour in a storage reactor. Therefore, in the present study, a numerical model for the CuO pellet-packed bed is developed and validated against experimental measurements. The validated model is used to enhance the understanding of the thermal and reactive behaviour of the bed. Further insights into ways to improve and optimize the reactor are provided by performing a parametric study using the validated model.

2. Numerical modelling

A lab-scale CuO pellet-packed bed reactor was designed and experimentally investigated by Gigantino et al. [28] in which the thermochemical redox cycle of $\text{CuO}/\text{Cu}_2\text{O}$ pair was examined in isobaric and isothermal operational modes. In the isobaric redox cycles, each cycle consisted of a charging phase during which the air inflow temperature was increased to a desired set point above the onset temperature of reduction, followed by a discharging phase during which the air inflow temperature was decreased to a set-point value of $870 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In the isothermal redox cycles, the cycle was performed by varying the oxygen partial pressure of the inlet gas flow while keeping its temperature constant. The reactor was initially preheated with an airflow of constant temperature reaching a quasi-steady state. Then gas flow was switched to nitrogen to activate the reduction and air to trigger the oxidation. Charging and discharging phases were alternated by switching the gas inflow to nitrogen and air, respectively.

Fig. 2 shows the schematics of the experimental apparatus mainly including a pellet-packed reactor, a heating element, insulation,

Fig. 2. Schematics of the reaction unit (adapted from Ref. [28]).

etc. The reactor is made of a quartz tube with an inner diameter of 50 mm. The tube was packed with CuO pellets which were synthesized using CuO powders and Y₂O₃-stabilized ZrO₂ (YSZ) powders, i.e., 50 wt% CuO-YSZ pellets. The CuO pellets mentioned in the following represent 50 wt% CuO-YSZ pellets. The reactive bed composed of CuO pellets has a height of 40 mm and a porosity of 0.4067. To diminish radiation heat loss from the CuO pellets to the ambient, YSZ beads were packed right above the CuO pellets, i.e., an inert bed of a height of 60 mm and a porosity of 0.3833. Meanwhile, the reactive bed was supported by a porous quartz disk. Gas, flowing through a silicon-infiltrated silicon carbide (SiSiC), was heated by an electric furnace which mimicked concentrated solar heating, and then went into the reactive bed crossing quartz wool which helped to distribute the flow uniformly. The reactor was thermally insulated using multi-layer insulation to decrease heat loss, including glass wool blanket, pyrogenic insulation, and fire bricks. The present simulation was carried out based on the reactor shown in Fig. 2, and Table 1 summarizes important dimensions of the reactor.

2.1. Model description

To reliably simulate heat and mass transfer in the thermochemical heat storage unit as described in Fig. 2, several physical processes need to be considered, e.g., gas flow in free zones, gas flow in porous zones (SiSiC foam, quartz wool, quartz disk, reactive bed, and inert bed), heat transport in the pellet-packed bed, and chemical reactions in the bed.

2.1.1. Fluid flow model

Referring to the volumetric flow rate in reference [28], Reynolds number was calculated to determine the flow modes, i.e., laminar or turbulent, as

$$Re = \frac{\rho 4V / (\pi D_{rb}^2) D_{rb}}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

Where, the volumetric flow rate V is 10 L/min, and the reactor diameter D_{rb} is 50 mm. Accordingly, the Reynolds number was estimated as 272, using air properties at 25 °C. Because the air density decreases and viscosity increases with increasing temperature, the Reynolds number is even lower at the practical working temperature to stimulate the redox reaction. Therefore, laminar flow was assumed for the present free and porous flow. The flow in the free and the porous domain was described by the Navier-Stokes equations and the Brinkman equations, respectively. Thus.

- For the free-media flow, the governing equations are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{U}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \rho \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{U} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \left[\mu (\nabla \mathbf{U} + \nabla \mathbf{U}^T) - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}) \mathbf{I} \right] + \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (3)$$

- For the porous-media flow, the governing equations are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{U}) = S_m \quad (4)$$

Table 1

A few geometric parameters of the TCES unit.

Reactive bed (packed 50 wt% CuO-YSZ pellets)	
The diameter of the CuO-YSZ pellets, D_{pe}	1 mm
The porosity of the CuO-YSZ pellets, ε_{pe}	0.63
The weight of the reactive material, m_{rm}	107 g
The porosity of the reactive bed, ε_{rb}	0.4067
The initial surface site density of CuO, $c_{surf, CuO, init}$	21490 mol/m ²
The specific surface area of the reactive bed, A_s	3.984×10^7 m ⁻¹
The diameter of the reactive bed, D_{rb}	50 mm
The height of the reactive bed, h_{rb}	40 mm
Inert bed (packed YSZ beads) and others	
The diameter of the YSZ beads, D_{bead}	2.3 mm
The porosity of the inert bed, ε_{ib}	0.3833
The height of the inert bed, h_{ib}	60 mm
The height of the quartz disk, h_{qd}	2.5 mm
The porosity of the quartz disk, ε_{qd}	0.1
The height of the quartz wool, h_{qw}	20 mm
The porosity of the quartz wool, ε_{qw}	0.9682
The porosity of the SiSiC foam, ε_{SiSiC}	0.84
The diameter of the gas inlet, D_{inlet}	14 mm

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \rho \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla \frac{\mathbf{U}}{\varepsilon} = -\varepsilon \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \left[\mu (\nabla \mathbf{U} + \nabla \mathbf{U}^T) - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}) \mathbf{I} \right] - \left(\varepsilon \frac{\mu}{\kappa} + \frac{S_m}{\varepsilon} \right) \mathbf{U} + \varepsilon \rho \mathbf{g} \quad (5)$$

Where \mathbf{I} is the unit tensor. ε is the porosity and κ is the permeability that was estimated by the Kozeny-Carman model. S_m is a mass source for species, e.g., oxygen consumption or generation in the reactive porous domain. \mathbf{U} is the velocity vector. μ is the fluid viscosity, and ρ is the fluid density.

2.1.2. Heat transfer model

In this study, heat transfer was considered in several domains, including thermal insulation, free flow domain, porous reactive domain (CuO pellet-packed domain), and porous non-reactive domains (SiSiC foam, quartz wool, inert bed).

- In thermal insulation, there are no convection and heat sources. Heat transfer is determined by thermal conduction, which was expressed as

$$\rho_{\text{ins}} C_{p,\text{ins}} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \lambda_{\text{ins}} \nabla T \quad (6)$$

where ρ_{ins} and $C_{p,\text{ins}}$ are the density and heat capacity of the thermal insulation material, respectively. λ_{ins} is the thermal conductivity of the thermal insulation material.

- In the free flow domain, the rate of energy change depends on the heat flux into the domain by convection and conduction, and the rate of work done. Therefore, the energy equation is given as

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho C_p \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla T - \nabla \cdot \lambda \nabla T = \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \left\{ \left[\mu (\nabla \mathbf{U} + \nabla \mathbf{U}^T) - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}) \mathbf{I} \right] \cdot \mathbf{U} \right\} \quad (7)$$

- In the porous media domain, it was supposed that heat was transported by the thermal convection between the fluid and solid, the thermal conduction, and thermal radiation between pellets, as shown in Fig. 3. Two energy equations were established for the solid

Fig. 3. Heat transfer mechanism in the reactive pellet-packed bed.

and fluid phases, respectively, which were supposed to be in a thermal non-equilibrium state. Accordingly, the energy equation was solved separately for the fluid and solid.

$$\varepsilon\rho C_p \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + \rho C_p \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla T_f - \nabla \cdot \varepsilon \lambda \nabla T_f = \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla p + \nabla \cdot \left\{ \left[\mu (\nabla \mathbf{U} + \nabla \mathbf{U}^T) - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}) \mathbf{I} \right] \cdot \mathbf{U} \right\} + \alpha_{fs} A_s (T_f - T_s) + S_h \quad (8)$$

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \rho_s C_{p,s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (1 - \varepsilon) \lambda_{eff} \nabla T_s = \alpha_{fs} A_s (T_s - T_f) + S_h \quad (9)$$

Where ε is the porosity of the domain. α_{fs} is the interstitial convective heat transfer coefficient. A_s is the specific surface area of the porous domain. α_{fs} is the interstitial heat transfer coefficient. S_h is the thermochemical heat which only exists in the reactive porous domain while it is excluded from equations (8) and (9) in the other porous domains.

It is worth noting that an effective thermal conductivity was used in equation (9). The effective thermal conductivity accounts for the thermal conductivity of the pellet-packed bed and the heat radiation occurring inside the bed. Concerning the pellet-packed bed, its thermal conductivity is not the value of pure materials (pellets) due to its porous characteristics. The thermal conductivity of the bed could be calculated using Krupiczka equation [40], as below

$$\lambda_{ms} = \lambda_f \left(\frac{\lambda_s}{\lambda_f} \right)^{0.28 - 0.757 \log \varepsilon - 0.057 \log(\lambda_s/\lambda_f)} \quad (10)$$

Meanwhile, the radiative heat transfer cannot be omitted in the porous domain due to high operating temperatures (>1000 K). For the optically thick porous media, the heat radiation can be included by adding a thermal conductivity term in the conduction equation, accounting for the heat radiation. In this study, the Rosseland approximation was used [41], which is formulated as

$$\lambda_R = \frac{16n^2\sigma^3}{3\beta} \quad (11)$$

Where n is the refractive index which is around 1 for air, and β is the Rosseland extinction coefficient of the solid material. Then the final effective thermal conductivity used in equation (9) is calculated as

$$\lambda_{eff} = \lambda_{ms} + \lambda_R \quad (12)$$

2.1.3. Species transport model

In this study, heat storage and release were achieved by a reversible redox reaction of CuO/Cu₂O. The CuO was prepared as pellets that were packed in a reaction bed. In the heat storage (charging) process, N₂ was preheated by an oven at a temperature of 950 °C when flowing through the SiSiC foam and then enters the pellet bed to activate the reduction. CuO was reduced to Cu₂O and O₂ was released. Correspondingly, in the oxidation (discharging) process, air preheated by the oven passes through the pellet bed and reacts with Cu₂O to release heat. The chemical reaction formula is shown below

In the simulation, CuO and Cu₂O were regarded as surface species on pellets. They can be produced and consumed in the reaction. Oxygen was transported by airflow, which could be governed by a species transport equation. The rate of change of oxygen concentration results from the convective transport, species diffusion, and production/consumption due to the chemical reaction. The species transport equation is given as

$$\varepsilon \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (c_i) + \mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla c_i + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_i = R_i \quad (14)$$

Where c_i is the molar concentration of bulk species (mol/m³). \mathbf{J}_i is the tensor that accounts for diffusion and dispersion, expressed as $-(D_{d,i} + D_{e,i}) \nabla c_i$, and R_i is the volumetric reaction rate (mol/(m³·s)) that accounts for the reaction. ε is the porosity of the pellet bed.

In addition to oxygen which is bulk species, surface species, i.e., CuO and Cu₂O, were also considered. The surface density change of the surface species could be expressed by the species governing equation inside the pellet. A few assumptions such as the surface species being immobile and the pellet being spherical, were made to formulate the surface species governing equation. The surface density of the surface species only changes along the radial direction while no density variation in the space-angle direction. Then, the change rate of the surface density depends on the diffusion of the gas into the pellet to advance the reaction, and reaction rate. The equation describing the surface species is written as

$$\varepsilon_{pe} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (c_{pe,i}) + \frac{1}{r_{pe}^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(-r^2 D_{pe,i} \frac{c_{pe,i}}{\partial r} \right) = A_{pe} R_{pe,i}^s \quad (15)$$

Where $c_{pe,i}$ is the volumetric site density of the surface species (mol/m³). r_{pe} is the radius of the spherical pellet. A_{pe} is the specific surface area of the pellet (m⁻¹). $R_{pe,i}^s$ is the surface reaction rate (mol/(m²·s)). ε_{pe} is the porosity of the pellet.

2.1.4. Reaction kinetics model

The reaction kinetics of the CuO/Cu₂O pair has to be correctly modelled so that the reaction rate can be calculated to close the

governing equations above. The present study used the kinetic model developed by Deutsch et al. [27] who experimentally investigated the reaction kinetics of the CuO/Cu₂O reaction cycle using a simultaneous thermal analysis and a lab-scale pellet-packed-bed reactor. A non-parametric kinetic (NPK) approach was used to develop the kinetics model. The approach relies on the singular value decomposition for the experimental data processing, and establishes the kinetics model, getting rid of empirical coefficients and the Arrhenius law. Normally, the conversion rate of species in the redox reaction depends on the conversion (ψ) and temperature (T), which is expressed as

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = f(\psi)k(T) \quad (16)$$

The conversion ψ is defined as the ratio of generated oxygen to the theoretical amount of oxygen that can be generated, as discussed in Ref. [27]. The measurement could provide a data set including ψ , T , and $d\psi/dt$ which can be written as a matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} f(\psi_1)k(T_1) & \cdots & f(\psi_1)k(T_m) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f(\psi_n)k(T_1) & \cdots & f(\psi_n)k(T_m) \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

Then the matrix \mathbf{A} could be processed by the singular value decomposition (SVD) to reduce the data dimensions and extract the most important information, as

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{S}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{V}^T = \sum_1^{\min(m,n)} \mathbf{S}(i)\mathbf{W}(i)\mathbf{V}^T(i) \quad (18)$$

Where i represents the column number of the matrix. The matrix \mathbf{W} is a diagonal matrix and the element value decreases along the diagonal. equation (16) indicates that only the first entry of \mathbf{W} is significantly larger than zero. Thus, the matrix \mathbf{A} can be written as

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{S}(1)\mathbf{W}(1)\mathbf{V}^T(1) = \mathbf{s}\mathbf{w}\mathbf{v}^T \quad (19)$$

Where \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{v}^T are the first column of the matrix \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{V}^T , respectively, while w is the first entry of the matrix \mathbf{W} .

Deutsch et al. [27] reported the ψ -dependent vector \mathbf{s} and T -dependent vector \mathbf{v}^T for the CuO/Cu₂O reaction in a pellet-packed bed. Then, a kinetic model was established in this study by extracting data there. A 2D-grid file was generated and uploaded in COMSOL to estimate the conversion rate. Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the conversion rate and the temperature as well as the conversion.

In principle, the heat source of the reaction is dependent on the enthalpy of formation of species and the reaction rate of the creation of species. In this study, it is defined as

$$S_h = -\frac{d\psi}{dt} \frac{c_{\text{surf_CuO_init}}}{4} \bullet rH^0 \quad (20)$$

H^0 is the standard enthalpy change of the reaction at 298.15 K (283 kJ/mol) which is multiplied by a factor r to account for the enhanced enthalpy change at the equilibrium temperature of the reaction. $c_{\text{surf_CuO_init}}$ is the initial surface concentration density of CuO which is 21490 mol/m².

2.2. Simulation domain and mesh

In this study, a 2D numerical model is developed to investigate the thermochemical heat storage performance of CuO/Cu₂O. Fig. 2 demonstrates the reactor configuration which is the object of interest. Considering the symmetric characteristics of the reactor, half of the reactor was chosen as the simulation domain which can fully present the physical processes but reduce the computational load, as shown in Fig. 5. The simulation domain is composed of a flow channel, a heater, and thermal insulation. The flow channel has an inlet/outlet free-flow section and porous media zones including SiSiC foam, quartz wool, quartz disk, reactive bed, and inert bed. When the gas passed through the SiSiC foam, it was heated by the heater. The heated gas then reached the reactive bed (CuO pellet-packed bed), having the redox reaction. To reduce heat losses, the reactor was wrapped with three layers of thermal insulation marked by the solid

Fig. 4. Reaction kinetics of the CuO/Cu₂O redox reaction: the dependence of the conversion rate on temperature and conversion.

Fig. 5. Simulation domain and mesh.

green/blue/grey colour. Table 2 summarizes the thermal properties of the materials involved in this study, i.e., CuO/Cu₂O [42], YSZ [43], SiSiC [44], quartz wool [45], glass wool blanket [46], pyrogenic insulation [47], and fire brick [48].

Quadrilateral meshes were generated separately in the flow domain and non-flow domain. In the flow domain, structured quadrilateral mesh was generated by adding mapped nodes, with fined boundary layer meshes. In the domain of insulation and the cavity with heaters, the unstructured quadrilateral mesh was generated by adding free quad nodes. The maximum mesh size was controlled as 3.0 mm, while the minimum mesh size was controlled as 0.12 mm. The maximum mesh growth rate was 1.3. Fig. 5 also shows the mesh in different domains, with an average element quality of around 0.989, indicating a high quality.

2.3. Boundary conditions

To solve the governing equations above, boundary conditions have to be given. Fig. 5 also demonstrates the main boundary conditions including symmetry axis, gas inlet, reactor inlet, gas outlet, reactor outlet, and walls, which are summarized in Table 3.

2.3.1. Inlet and outlet boundary conditions

The current model involved multi-physical processes including fluid flow, heat transfer, and species transport (reaction). To solve the continuous equation and momentum equation, a mass flow rate was given at the gas inlet, and a gauge pressure of zero was set at the gas outlet. The mass flow rate was calculated based on the volume flow rate of the measurement [28]. To solve the species transport equation, an oxygen concentration was defined at the reactor inlet, and a diffusive transport flux of zero was given at the reactor outlet. The current simulation was for an isokinetic redox cycle, meaning that the gas temperature on the reactor inlet was kept constant but the oxygen concentration (partial pressure) at the reactor inlet was varied. The whole process was divided into three phases, i.e., preheating phase (100 min), reduction phase (120 min), and oxidation phase (30 min) which were the same as those in the measurement. In the preheating phase, the reactor was heated by an airflow, and a nitrogen flow was used in the reduction phase while an air flow was used in the oxidation phase. Accordingly, the oxygen concentration at the reactor inlet was 0 and 8.6 mol/m³ (0.21 atm) at the reduction and oxidation phases, respectively. In terms of the thermal boundary condition, a constant temperature of 293.15 K was set at the gas inlet, while a temperature gradient of zero was given at the gas outlet.

2.3.2. Wall boundary conditions

There were inside walls, external walls, and heater walls which were all non-slippery. The external wall included the side wall, top wall, and bottom wall on which a convective heat flux boundary condition was applied, accounting for the heat loss, expressed as $q = h_{nc}(T_w - T_{ambient})$. h_{nc} is the convective heat transfer coefficient. On the side wall, h_{nc} was defined as that of external natural convection on cylinder side surfaces while concerning h_{nc} on the top wall and bottom wall, it was the external natural convective heat transfer coefficient on the top surface and bottom surface of hot plates, respectively.

The heater wall had a constant temperature of 950 °C to mimic the set-point furnace temperature in the measurement. Since the

Table 2
Thermal properties of the materials.

Material	ρ (kg/m ³)	C_p (J/kg·K)	λ (W/m·K)
CuO	6315	$10^{-7} T^3 - 0.005T^2 + 0.6904T + 374.18$	33
Cu ₂ O	6000	$2 \times 10^{-7} T^3 - 0.005T^2 + 0.562T + 309.28$	6.28
YSZ (Y ₂ O ₃ -stabilized ZrO ₂)	6100	$-0.0002T^2 + 0.5331T + 332.96$	2
Reactive pellets	$0.5(1-\alpha)\rho_{CuO} + \alpha\rho_{Cu2O} + 0.5\rho_{YSZ}$	$0.5(1-\alpha)C_{p,CuO} + \alpha C_{p,Cu2O} + 0.5 C_{p,YSZ}$	$\lambda_f \times (\lambda_s/\lambda_f)^{(0.28-0.757\log_{10}(erb) - 0.057\log_{10}(\lambda_s/\lambda_f)}$ $\lambda_s = 0.5(1-\alpha)\lambda_{CuO} + \alpha\lambda_{Cu2O} + 0.5\lambda_{YSZ}$ $\lambda_f = 0.07821$
SiSiC foam	480	700	6
Quartz wool/disk	2210	730	0.038/1.26
Glass wool blanket	128	1130	$3 \times 10^{-7}T^2 - 0.0002T + 0.0457$
Pyrogenic insulation	220	1080	$4 \times 10^{-8}T^2 - 0.00005T + 0.0299$
Fire brick	390	1050	$2 \times 10^{-7}T^2 - 0.0002T + 0.1452$

Table 3
Boundary conditions.

Boundary condition	Thermal	Flow	Chemistry
Symmetry axis	$\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = 0$	$\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} = 0, u_r = 0,$ $\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial r} = 0$	$\frac{\partial c_{O_2}}{\partial r} = 0$
Gas inlet	$T = 293.15 \text{ K}$	Constant mass flow rate	–
Gas outlet	$\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0$	$p = 1 \text{ atm}$	–
Inlet of the reactive packed bed	–	–	$c_{O_2} = \begin{cases} 0, \text{ when reduction} \\ 8.63 \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3}, \text{ when oxidation} \end{cases}$
Outlet of the reactive packed bed	–	–	$\frac{\partial c_{O_2}}{\partial x} = 0$
External wall: side wall, bottom wall, and top wall	$q = h_{nc}(T_w - T_{ambient})$ h_{nc} is the external natural convection heat transfer coefficient of the cylinder side surface or top/bottom of hot plates	No slip	–
Heater wall	$T = 1223.15 \text{ K}$ $q = h_{nc}(T_w - T_{air})$ h_{nc} is the external natural convection heat transfer coefficient of parallel plates	No slip	–
Tube wall	$q = h_{fc}(T_w - T_f)$ h_{fc} is the forced convective heat transfer coefficient which could be estimated based on Nusselt number which is 3.66 for laminar flow	No slip	–

heater was in a cavity filled with air, heat transfer from the heater to the air was assumed to be natural convection, similar to the case of the internal natural convection between parallel plates.

Concerning the tube wall, a heat flux condition was given to account for the heat transfer between the wall and fluid in the tube, expressed as $q = h_{fc}(T_w - T_f)$. h_{fc} is the forced convective heat transfer coefficient which could be estimated based on Nusselt number (i.e., 3.66 in laminar flow). Meanwhile, surface-to-surface radiation was considered between the tube wall of the SiSiC foam part and the heater wall, and the net radiative heat flux to the tube wall was $G - J$. G is the irradiation while J is the outgoing radiation.

The governing equations were solved by a finite element method with the boundary conditions, which were implemented by COMSOL Multiphysics 6.0.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, the model was validated, and then the model was used to reveal the temperature and reaction evolution over time in the pellet-packed bed. Such insights could provide some guidance for the design of the reactive bed, e.g., near-wall treatment to enhance heat transfer. In addition, with the validated model, parameter studies were conducted, including inlet mass flow rate, reduction temperature, and oxidation temperature. The parameter study demonstrates the reactor performance under different conditions.

3.1. Model validation

Mesh independent study was first implemented. Four grid systems were generated by changing the mesh size and mesh refinement, i.e., grid 1, grid 2, grid 3, and grid 4 which have 22842 meshes, 13557 meshes, 8744 meshes, and 6517 meshes, respectively. Fig. 6

Fig. 6. Study of grid independence.

compares the numerical result of the porous solid temperature at the reactor inlet (T_1). It is seen that the result of grid 1 only slightly differs from that of grid 4, showing good mesh independence. In the following simulation, the grid system of 22842 was used.

The model was first used to simulate the redox cycle of CuO/Cu₂O in the isokinetic (isothermal) condition, with the same inputs as those in the experiment [28], e.g., inlet mass flow rate, furnace temperature, etc. Then, the numerical result was compared with the measurement concerning the solid temperature T_2 in the reactor (the pellet-packed bed), and the molar fraction of O₂ at the reactor outlet. Fig. 7 demonstrates that the results from the model and experiment coincide with each other well in 3 redox cycles, within 10% discrepancy. Therefore, the model was well-validated and could be convincingly used for further study.

3.2. Reaction bed temperature profile and reaction progress

The reaction performance depends on the temperature of the redox material, as discussed in the section on reaction kinetics. The solid temperature in the pellet-packed bed was extracted, and the transient temperature fields were compared. Fig. 8 shows the temperature changing against time in the reduction phase (endothermic charging). It is seen that the material temperature is high in the middle region and low in the side region, generating a parabolic likewise profile. A significant temperature gradient is recognized in the middle region. The high-temperature front moves quickly along the mainstream direction, with slow evolution along the radial direction. Such temperature performance depends on the flow and heat transfer in the pellet-packed bed. On the one hand, heat losses exist on the bed wall, which lowers the heat dissipated to the reactive material from the gas near the wall (the side region). On the other hand, the flow distribution in the pellet-packed bed is uneven, causing less heat flux to the radially outward side of the reactive material and inefficient heat transfer on the side region. Furthermore, it is speculated that the temperature characteristics are affected by the changing thermal properties of the material due to the reaction. Cu₂O has a much smaller thermal conductivity than CuO, while the heat capacity of Cu₂O is also smaller than that of CuO at high temperatures (e.g., >1000 K). Therefore, when charging heat storage, a significant temperature gradient appears in the region where the reduction reaction of CuO to Cu₂O occurs. In contrast to the temperature profile in the reduction process, Fig. 9 demonstrates the temperature characteristics in the oxidation phase (exothermic discharging). It is seen that the temperature field considerably changes from $t = 221$ min to $t = 223$ min, corresponding to the onset of the oxidation reaction. A high-temperature region (around 1250–1400 K) appears in the central area while a relatively low-temperature region (around 1150–1250 K) occurs close to the reactor wall. Still, the heat loss through the reactor wall and the downstream inert bed accounts for the temperature performance. Additionally, it is due to non-uniform reaction rates over the domain. As shown in Fig. 9(a), the temperature near the wall is relatively low at the initial stage of the oxidation. The exothermic oxidation is then supposed to run fast near the wall, generating more CuO in this region. Similar to the statement earlier, Cu₂O in the central region has a large temperature rise while CuO near the wall has a small temperature rise, as heated by the discharging heat, because of the different heat capacity. With time elapsing, the high-temperature region shrinks, indicating the propagation of the oxidation reaction. The reaction characteristics are discussed as follows.

The experimental measurement in the study [28] revealed the reactor performance from an overall perspective by measuring temperatures along the flow direction. Nonetheless, the reaction progress characteristics are not unveiled. In contrast, the numerical model proposed in this study could visualize the reaction progress by defining the extent of the reaction as

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{c_{\text{surf_CuO}}}{c_{\text{surf_CuO_init}}} \quad (21)$$

$c_{\text{surf_CuO_init}}$ and $c_{\text{surf_CuO}}$ are the initial site density of CuO and the instant site density of CuO on the surface, respectively. $\alpha =$

Fig. 7. Validation of the numerical model: (a) T_2 comparison between the simulation and experiment, (b) Molar fraction of O₂ comparison between the simulation and experiment.

Fig. 8. Temperature variation in the reduction process.

Fig. 9. Temperature variation in the oxidation process.

0 means no reduction or completion of oxidation. $\alpha = 1$ means no oxidation or completion of reduction. $0 < \alpha < 1$ indicates the reaction progress. Fig. 10 presents the extent of the reaction over time in one charging (reduction)-discharging (oxidation) cycle. As shown in Fig. 10(a), the reduction reaction has a highly non-uniform extent of the reaction over the reactor domain, indicating various reaction rates. The reduction runs fastest in the middle region and gets slowly from the center to the wall and from the inlet to the outlet, as shown by the decreasing extent of the reaction. By comparing it with the temperature profile in Fig. 8, it is seen that a high temperature corresponds to a quick reduction (a large value of α), and vice versa, which is consistent with the finding in the literature [39] which investigated the reduction of iron-manganese oxide particles in a packed-bed reactor. In terms of the oxidation process in Fig. 10(b), it takes place on the whole domain of the reactor, but with a location-dependent reaction rate. For example, the extent of the oxidation decreases to zero (completion) in 2 min near the reactor wall (from $t = 200$ min to $t = 223$ min), while it is around 0.65 in the central region, indicating a high oxidation rate near the wall. The oxidation gradually develops from the near-wall region to the central region. Again by comparing Fig. 10(b) and Fig. 9, it is found that the oxidation runs quickly in the relatively low-temperature region, which is different from the reduction. The dependence of the reaction rate on the temperature matches with the reaction kinetics described in Fig. 4. All in all, the reaction propagates in a way following the temperature footprint. Therefore, based on such insights, it is recommended to organize the pellets in a way that has the desired thermal-hydraulic performance and then makes the overall reaction run steadily and quickly. Thermal insulation materials should also be screened.

Fig. 10. Reaction propagation against time: (a) reduction, (b) oxidation.

3.3. Parametric study

The reactor performance is affected by many parameters, e.g., reactor geometry and operation conditions [32]. The present study targets a pellet-packed bed reactor, and attention is paid to the operation parameters, e.g., inlet mass flow rates, and heating boundary conditions. These parameters are prone to vary in practical applications for performance optimization, which will be investigated in this section. The reactor performance is characterized by output temperatures and the extent of the reaction. As introduced above, the extent of the reaction accounts for the reaction progress representing the amount of charging/discharging heat. The output temperature indicates the grade of the charging/discharging heat. The profile of output temperature also tells the stability of the reactor performance. In some applications, e.g., Air-Brayton cycle concentrated solar power plant, high output temperatures are desired which corresponds to high efficiencies of the power generation cycle.

The mass flow rate considerably affects the flow and heat transfer in the pellet-packed bed and accordingly influences the reactor performance. In this study, five mass flow rates were considered, i.e., 0.10 g/s, 0.15 g/s, 0.20 g/s, 0.30 g/s, and 0.40 g/s, while the other parameters were kept the same, e.g., furnace temperature, pellet diameter, reaction bed porosity, specific surface area, etc. The reactor experienced three processes in one complete cycle, i.e., a preheating process, a reduction charging process, and an oxidation discharging process. In the preheating process, a period of 100 min was assumed for the material (CuO) preheated by air passing through a furnace with a constant set-point temperature of 1223 K. Then, the redox reaction was implemented with a pressure-swing (isothermal) mode. The charging and discharging phases were alternated by switching the gas inflow to nitrogen and air, respectively. In this study, the reduction duration and the oxidation duration were controlled at 120 min and 30 min, respectively, consistent with the experimental campaign in the literature [28]. Fig. 11 compares the extent of the reaction against time in one cycle. It is found that the reduction runs faster with increasing flow rate, and full conversion only completes at the flow rate of 0.30 g/s and 0.40 g/s. As

Fig. 11. The effect of the mass flow rate on the extent of the reaction over time.

discussed earlier, the reduction speed depends on the material temperature, and it proceeds quickly with high temperatures. Thus the material temperature T_2 is compared, as shown in Fig. 12. Interestingly, the material temperatures at the flow rates of 0.30 g/s and 0.40 g/s are almost the same but higher than those of the other flow rates during the reduction. As a consequence, the reduction progresses the most quickly at the flow rates of 0.30 g/s and 0.40 g/s, which validates the performance of the extent of the reaction. During the oxidation, initially, the material temperatures at the flow rates of 0.30 g/s and 0.40 g/s are also almost the same but smaller than those of the other flow rates. The reaction kinetics in Fig. 4(b) indicate that the oxidation runs faster at a relatively low temperature. Thus, the curve of α drops the most sharply at the flow rate of 0.30 g/s and 0.40 g/s in Fig. 11.

Fig. 13 compares the outlet temperature at different mass flow rates. It is seen that at the preheating stage, the output temperature increases with increasing mass flow rate because the large flow rate promotes the interstitial heat transfer between the gas and the SiSiC foam in the furnace [49], which transfers more heat to the gas within a limited time. In theory, the temperature at the pre-heating stage could converge if allowed to heat up indefinitely, but the pre-heating process was not sufficient enough to achieve this convergence. During the reduction process, the output temperature drops initially because the reduction reaction extracts heat from the gas. The drop amplitude depends on the extent of the reaction. The full reduction is only achieved at 0.30 g/s and 0.40 g/s inducing a relatively large drop in the output temperature. The output temperature is relatively steady at the low mass flow rate of 0.10 g/s during the reduction, because the amount of charging heat is the least in this case as a result of the smallest extent of the reduction. Similarly, at the exothermic oxidation stage, the output temperature rises because of the discharging heat. The temperature rise is almost the same in the current cases, but the enthalpy increases the least at the lowest flow rates because the reactor suffers from incomplete reduction and then there is less reactive material available for oxidation.

3.3.1. The influence of reduction temperature on the reactor performance

In addition to the mass flow rates, the effect of heating conditions on the reactor performance was also examined. This section explores the impact of temperature variation during the reduction while the oxidation temperature is kept constant at 1223 K. The mass flow rate was also kept the same as that in the validation case (0.216 g/s). The reduction temperature varied from 1123 K to 1323 K, above the equilibrium temperature of CuO/Cu₂O. Fig. 14 shows the extent of the reaction over time. The higher reduction temperature increases the reaction progress in a similar way as the mass flow rate. Within the given reduction duration, only the reduction temperature of 1273 K and 1323 K achieve full conversion, while the reduction is not completed in the other cases. In terms of oxidation, it shows minor differences because oxidation temperature is kept constant in each case. To validate the conjecture concerning the material temperature performance, Fig. 15 reveals the material temperature at the location T_2 . Evidently, the material has a high temperature during the reduction when increasing the reduction temperature. Since the set-point temperature of the furnace was kept the same during the oxidation, the material temperature was almost the same at the oxidation stage, as shown in Fig. 16. Such temperature characteristics account for the performance of the extent of the reaction.

Fig. 16 demonstrates the output temperature profile at the different reduction temperatures. It is found that a high reduction temperature leads to a high output temperature as expected. At the beginning of the reduction stage, the output temperature experiences a sharp decrease, e.g., at 1323 K, because of the fast heat-charging behavior described in Fig. 15. When the charging gets slow, the output temperature increases to approach a quasi-steady state. At the low reduction temperature of 1123 K, the output temperature is relatively steady in the whole reduction process, because the charging is slow and the heat charged from the gas to the reactive material could be compensated by the incoming heat flux. Similar to the case of mass flow rate, a temperature peak also appears in the oxidation process, which is due to a quick initial discharging behavior. It is also seen that at the end of the oxidation, the plot tends to converge as the input temperature and mass flow rate are equal at that moment.

3.3.2. The influence of oxidation temperature on the reactor performance

The earlier section concentrates on the reduction temperature, while the effect of the oxidation temperature on the reactor performance is investigated in this section. In the study, the set-point temperature of the furnace was varied during the oxidation (named oxidation temperature). The mass flow rate and the reduction temperature were kept constant at 0.216 g/s and 1223 K, respectively. Thus, the reactor achieved the same performance at the pre-heating and reduction stage regardless of the oxidation temperature, reaching an almost full reduction of $\alpha = 0.97$ and output temperature of ~ 1142 K before entering the oxidation process. As a consequence, the reactor performance is only compared at the oxidation stage. Fig. 17(a) compares the extent of the reaction at the oxidation stage under the oxidation temperatures of 1198 K, 1223 K, and 1253 K. It shows that the oxidation rate slightly differs between the cases, while the low oxidation temperature results in a slightly quicker oxidation at 1198 K. As extensively discussed in the previous sections, the oxidation rate depends on the material temperature. The material temperature is slightly lower at the oxidation temperature of 1198 K than the other cases, leading to a slight increase in the oxidation rate. The increase makes the reaction complete earlier than in the other cases thereby shifting the output temperature peak, as shown in Fig. 17 (b). After the completion of the oxidation process, the output temperature mainly depends on the sensible heating temperature.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a multi-physics model was established to investigate the heat storage performance of a CuO-pellet-packed bed. The model involves flow and heat transfer in free and porous media domains as well as chemical reactions. It is validated using the experimental results and further used to do parameter studies. A few conclusions are summarized as follows.

Fig. 12. Comparison of the reactive material temperature at different mass flow rates.

Fig. 13. The effect of the mass flow rate on the output temperature.

Fig. 14. The effect of the set-point furnace temperature during the reduction (reduction temperature) on the extent of the reaction against time.

- 1) Radiation is an important heat transfer mechanism in the pellet-packed bed. The radiation could be simulated as extra heat conduction, using the Rosseland approximation method to modify the thermal conductivity. The reaction kinetics model is established by the non-parametric kinetic (NPK) approach, which well describes the reaction rate, depending on the temperature and conversion.
- 2) The reaction dynamics depend on the reactive material temperature characteristics. In the reduction process (charging), the reactive material temperature is high in the middle region and low in the side region. The high-temperature front moves quickly along the mainstream direction, with slow evolution along the radial direction. Accordingly, the reaction propagates in a way following the temperature footprint, with a start at the inlet middle. The reaction then goes the most quickly in the middle region and gradually moves from the inlet to the outlet and from the middle to the side.
- 3) In the oxidation process (discharging), the temperature characteristics are different from those in the reduction process. The temperature is low in the area close to the reactor wall, and high in the central area. With time elapsing, the high-temperature

Fig. 15. Comparison of the reactive material temperature in conditions of various reduction temperatures.

Fig. 16. The effect of the reduction temperature on the output temperature.

Fig. 17. The effect of the set-point furnace temperature during the oxidation (oxidation temperature) on the reactor performance: (a) the extent of the reaction, (b) the output temperature.

region shrinks. Correspondingly, the oxidation reaction occurs and completes the earliest in the side region near the reactor wall. The reaction front fades inwardly from the side to the middle of the reactor and the oxidation rate near the wall is higher than that near the center.

- 4) The reduction/oxidation performance is affected by the mass flow rate of gas, the reduction temperature, and the oxidation temperature. Large mass flow rates and high reduction temperatures promote the reaction performance. For example, the large mass flow rate and high reduction temperatures correspond to high output temperature and fast reduction reaction because the large flow rate and high reduction temperature both increase the heating rate and the reactive material temperature. In comparison, the output temperature also increases with increasing oxidation temperature, and the oxidation reaction rate is slightly improved by decreasing the oxidation temperature in the concerned case.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zhen Cao: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Bas Joris de Leeuw:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Tianchao Xie:** Visualization, Software, Data curation. **Abhishek K. Singh:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Abhishek Kumar Singh reports financial support was provided by the European Commission, through the HORIZON EUROPE, RIA – Research and Innovation Actions programmes HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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